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Modelling marine heatwaves impact on shallow and upper mesophotic tropical coral reefs

To cite this article: Nicolas Colombi *et al* 2024 *Environ. Res. Lett.* **19** 124053

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LETTER

Modelling marine heatwaves impact on shallow and upper mesophotic tropical coral reefs

OPEN ACCESS

RECEIVED

6 September 2024

REVISED

11 October 2024

ACCEPTED FOR PUBLICATION

22 October 2024

PUBLISHED

15 November 2024

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Abstract

Coral reefs ecosystems, often compared to rain forests for their high biodiversity, are threatened by ocean warming causing coral bleaching when the symbiotic relationship between dinoflagellates and corals breaks under high ocean temperatures. Thermal stress from marine heatwaves (MHWs) occur both at the surface and subsurface with subsurface MHWs lasting longer with potentially higher cumulative intensities. However, global coral bleaching models generally ignore the differences in thermal stress between surface and sea-bed levels. Here, we define MHWs at sea-bed level to model coral bleaching with daily resolution from 6 May 1993 to 31 October 2023, for 9944 tropical coral reefs between 0 and 60 m depths. We show that deeper reefs experience on average higher thermal stress and bleaching compared to surface reefs. Using surface temperature data to model bleaching for deeper corals underestimates bleaching intensities by an average of $6\% \pm 9\%$ compared to the subsurface calibrated model. Our study is a starting point for more accurate coral bleaching modelling, providing additional evidence to reshape our perception of deeper coral reefs as potential refuges from climate change.

1. Introduction

Coral reefs ecosystems are frequently compared to rain forests, in view of the high biodiversity they sustain (Liu *et al* 2014). It is estimated that coral reefs may harbor about one third of all the marine species known to date (Reaka-Kudla 1997, 2001). Coral reefs offer coastal protection against floods, are a source of income, fishing and biochemicals (Carte 1996, van Zanten *et al* 2014) benefiting around 1 billion people (NOAA 2023).

At present, tropical coral reefs are facing different threats, among which coral bleaching is the most alarming one (Hughes *et al* 2017, Kayanne 2017). Coral bleaching happens when environmental stresses, primarily rising ocean temperatures (Liu *et al* 2014), disrupt the symbiotic relationship between dinoflagellates and corals.

In a changing climate, mesophotic coral reefs (30–150 m) were proposed to provide a refuge for shallow reefs (0–30 m) from rising sea surface temperatures (SSTs) (Rocha *et al* 2018). It has been argued that globally, mesophotic corals ecosystems are less likely to bleach compared to shallow reefs due to reduced irradiance, lower temperature (Lesser *et al* 2009) and presumed lower susceptibility to natural impacts (Rocha *et al* 2018). In recent times though, research is showing that deeper coral reefs are not immune to mass bleaching events (Eyal *et al* 2022). Mesophotic corals react differently to thermal stress compared to shallower coral reefs, and are potentially equally or even more vulnerable than shallow reefs (Eyal *et al* 2022). Additionally, according to Amaya *et al* (2023b), the duration and intensity of bottom marine heatwaves (MHW) at the sea-bed can differ strongly from those at the surface. Bottom

MHWs tend to last longer with higher intensities compared to surface MHWs (Amaya *et al* 2023b). Bottom MHWs can occur when MHWs in the surface mixed layer, formed mainly from air–sea heat fluxes, reductions in wind-driven mixing or from advective transport of warm waters in anomalous currents or eddies e.g. (Oliver *et al* 2021, Bian *et al* 2023), extend to the subsurface (Zhang *et al* 2023) and reach the sea bed on the continental shelf. Furthermore, bottom MHWs on the shelf can also occur without a surface MHW, for example from downwelling of warm waters (Schaeffer and Roughan 2017). They can be particularly intense in the thermocline below the mixed layer, where a vertical shift in water masses results in large temperature anomalies (Fragkopoulos *et al* 2023). Considering that 50%–80% of the world coral reefs are situated between 30 and 150 m (Eyal *et al* 2022), understanding the global bleaching behavior along the depth gradient, and identifying potential limitations of current global bleaching models, becomes crucial.

To date, most global coral bleaching models use SST to define the standard coral bleaching proxy, the degree heating week (DHW) (Hughes *et al* 2017, Kayanne 2017). This surface-based DHW is then often applied to deeper reefs (Hughes *et al* 2017, Kayanne 2017, Sully *et al* 2019). In this study, we investigate whether defining MHWs at sea-bed level could enhance the accuracy of coral bleaching modeling for shallow and upper mesophotic tropical reefs on a global scale. Furthermore, we investigate whether deeper reefs experience higher thermal stresses compared to their surface counterpart, potentially revealing a disparity in bleaching estimations between surface and depth calibrated models. The novelty of this research lies in the definition on a global level of a coral bleaching proxy using temperature time series at sea-bed level, as opposed to the surface level, as commonly done. In addition, compared to standard categorical coral bleaching models, our approach allows the quantitative prediction of coral bleaching with the associated uncertainty; thus offering hindcasting and forecasting applications.

2. Methods

2.1. Data

Bleaching records for shallow and upper mesophotic coral reefs were provided by the Global Coral Bleaching Database (van Woesik and Kratochwill 2022) covering the years 1980–2020. For this research, coral reef locations with unspecified depths were excluded, resulting in a database comprising 9944 unique geographical locations of coral reefs (red and blue circles in figure 1). Of these locations, 4113 had documented instances of bleaching between 1993 and 2020 (red circles in figure 1). In cases where multiple depths were recorded for the same location (latitude and longitude), we calculated the average depth.

Given that bleaching events were measured at different dates for some locations, our dataset comprises a total of 4594 coral bleaching records distributed over 4113 locations.

Ocean temperature data is obtained from the GLORYS12 global ocean eddy resolving reanalysis product (Jean-Michel *et al* 2021). The database includes ocean temperature from 1 January 1993 to 31 October 2023 on daily-mean temporal resolution. GLORYS12 reanalysis has weak regional biases (<0.4 °C) compared to the World Ocean Atlas 2013 climatology and *in-situ* observations (<0.1 °C) (Dréville *et al* 2023). The largest biases occur between 50 and 100 m depth, and in the northern Atlantic and Southern oceans, where no coral in our dataset is present (Dréville *et al* 2023). At the equator, temperatures are very consistent with observations along the depth gradient (Dréville *et al* 2023). The global average SST exhibits a weak warm bias of less than 0.1 °C (Dréville *et al* 2023). GLORYS12 was used for the analyses because it provides daily-mean temperature estimates at depth at fine spatial resolution and because it reproduces nearshore bottom temperatures and recent MHWs with fidelity, compared to other products (Fredston *et al* 2023, Amaya *et al* 2023a, 2023b).

2.2. Parameter estimation and optimization of DHW

The DHW (units of °C week) has become a standard metric in coral bleaching modeling. It has been widely used in local and global coral reef studies (Hughes *et al* 2017, Kayanne 2017).

To compute the DHW at a given day j , we defined temperature anomalies A_j as

$$A_j = \begin{cases} T_j - M & T_j > \beta \\ 0 & T_j \leq \beta, \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

where T_j represent daily mean temperature at the day j at the specific coral reef location, M represent the maximum monthly mean of the entire study period, from 1 January 1993 to 31 October 2023, at the same coral reef location, and β represent the bleaching threshold. Anomalies lower than the bleaching threshold are set to zero, as they are assumed to not produce sufficient thermal stress to induce coral bleaching (Kayanne 2017). From the above defined temperature anomalies, we computed the DHW on day j ,

$$\text{DHW}_j = \frac{1}{\omega} \sum_{i=j-\omega}^j A_i, \quad (2)$$

where ω represent the length (in days) of the accumulation window (AW) for which the daily temperature anomalies A_i were summed and divided by 7.

Consequently, the DHW informs us on the cumulative thermal stress experienced by coral reefs in the last ω days.

The traditional DHW algorithm was originally defined in the 1990s, accumulating temperature anomalies relative to the maximum monthly mean above a bleaching threshold of $\beta = +1^\circ\text{C}$ over an AW of $\omega = 84$ d (12 weeks) (Glynn and D’croz 1990, Jokiel and Coles 1990, Lachs *et al* 2021). The bleaching threshold of $\beta = +1^\circ\text{C}$ and AW of $\omega = 12$ weeks was calibrated on experimental evidence from Panama and the Caribbean (Lachs *et al* 2021). In 2020, DeCarlo (2020) proposed a modification of the two DHW parameters: the AW and the bleaching threshold. Adopting a weather forecast approach to coral bleaching, DeCarlo (2020) used the equitable threat score (ETS) to measure the performance of various DHW definitions, finding that by lowering the bleaching threshold to $\beta = 0^\circ\text{C}$ and by decreasing the AW to $\omega = 63$ d (9 weeks), the skills of coral bleaching forecasts increased. In 2021, by testing 243 DHW configurations, Lachs *et al* (2021) established that the best performing DHW parameters were a bleaching threshold below or equal to the MMM and an AW between 4 and 8 weeks, with peak performance at $\beta = 0^\circ\text{C}$ and $\omega = 56$ d (8 weeks).

To find the DHW parameters that maximize predictive skills, we tested 196 combinations (4×49) of 4 bleaching thresholds and 49 AWs. The bleaching thresholds ranged from -2°C to $+1^\circ\text{C}$, and the AW varied from 3 to 52 weeks. For each of the 196 DHW definitions, we converted all bleaching records (ranging from 0% to 100%) into a binary variable: ‘bleaching’ or ‘absence of bleaching’. We used a threshold, γ , to make this classification. For example, if $\gamma = 20\%$, records of 20% or higher were classified as ‘bleaching’ (1), and those below 20% were classified as ‘absence of bleaching’ (0). The categorical threshold γ was varied between 1% and 99%. To assess the classification skills of a specific parameter choice for a given categorical threshold, we discretized a range of DHW thresholds τ ranging from 0 to 100. Values above τ predicted ‘bleaching’, and values below predicted

Table 1. Definition of hit, miss and false alarm. Reproduced from DeCarlo (2020). CC BY 4.0.

	Observation	Prediction
Hit (H)	1	1
Miss (M)	1	0
False Alarm (FA)	0	1

‘absence of bleaching’. We evaluated these predictions using the ETS. For example, $\tau = 8^\circ\text{C}$ weeks would imply that all DHW values equal or greater than 8°C weeks would predict ‘bleaching’, while lower values would predict ‘absence of bleaching’. The τ value that maximized the ETS was recorded as the optimal $\tilde{\tau}_\gamma$ value for a given categorical threshold γ and DHW parameters (β and ω). The ETS (Paredes Trejo *et al* 2016) is defined as

$$\text{ETS} = \frac{H - H_r}{H + \text{FA} + M - H_r}, \quad (3)$$

where H stands for hits, M for miss, FA for false alarm (as displayed in table 1) and

$$H_r = \frac{(H + \text{FA}) \times (H + M)}{n}, \quad (4)$$

where n is the total number of records.

By testing 196 combinations of DHW parameters, we mapped the ETS score across the whole range of categorical thresholds for every combination of DHW parameters, that is, the AW and bleaching threshold.

We simplified the 3D optimization space shown in figure 2 by computing the maximal and cumulative ETS over the categorical threshold dimension. The resulting 2D space in figure 3 indicates the length of the AW ω and bleaching threshold β that maximized the model skills for a specific categorical threshold γ as well as over the entire γ range. This helps identify the DHW parameters β and ω that most accurately classify bleaching events of all intensities.

When predicting bleaching at specific intensities, two window lengths, 8 weeks and 22 weeks, perform similarly, though 22 weeks have a slightly higher ETS

(figure 3(b)). Regarding bleaching thresholds, a clear deviation is observed with $+1^\circ\text{C}$ standing out as a negative outlier compared to other thresholds, both in predicting specific intensities and across the entire range (figure 3(a)). Bleaching thresholds of 0°C , -1°C , and -2°C perform similarly, with -1°C yielding slightly better model performance for both specific intensities and overall bleaching intensities. The choice of the parameters to define the DHW was based on the AW and bleaching threshold which yield the highest cumulative ETS score displayed in figure 3(a), that is, the curve (bleaching threshold) with the highest peak and the x-value corresponding to such peak (the AW). Our analysis thus suggests that optimal model performance, evaluated with the cumulative ETS, is achieved by employing an AW of 18 weeks and a bleaching threshold of -1°C below the MMM for the subsurface temperature product, and similarly an AW of 19 weeks along with a bleaching threshold of -1°C for the surface product.

Aside from displaying the higher performing DHW metrics, figure 3(a) shows the sensitivity of the cumulative ETS, and therefore of the model, to the key parameters of this study, the AW and bleaching threshold. With a common peak at around 18 weeks for bleaching thresholds of 0°C , -1°C , and -2°C , and a smooth decrease in model performance moving away from such peak, the model is not highly sensitive to the AW but presents a clear boundary in the choice of the parameter. The bleaching threshold of -1°C has an average cumulative ETS across all AWs of 18.72 ± 1.38 , a peak of 21.19 corresponding to AW 18 and a minimum at 15.45 corresponding to AW 3, with a gradual increase from AW 3 to 18, a linear decrease from AW 18 to 36 and stabilizing after AW 36.

Defining the DHW with a bleaching threshold of $\beta = -1^\circ\text{C}$ and an AW of $\omega = 18$ weeks, the optimal DHW threshold τ for a given categorical threshold γ was obtained by taking the DHW threshold value τ which maximizes the ETS for that

Figure 3. (a) Cumulative ETS across all categorical thresholds, indicating the accumulation window which maximize predicting skills across every bleaching intensity. (b) Maximal ETS across all categorical thresholds, indicating the accumulation window which maximize predicting skills for a specific bleaching intensity.

Table 2. Sigmoid fitting parameters.

	Slope (s)	center (c)
Surface	0.275 770 55	17.142 933 70
Subsurface	0.289 753 83	16.527 656 66

particular categorical threshold. This procedure was repeated for every categorical threshold between $\gamma = 1\%$ and $\gamma = 99\%$ with 1% increments. The resulting pairs of categorical thresholds and optimal DHW thresholds were fitted with a sigmoid (equation (5) and table 2) and are graphically represented in figure 4.

$$f(x) = \frac{100}{1 + e^{-s*(x-c)}} \quad (5)$$

In a next step, we computed the DHW with the above defined parameter choice with daily resolution from 6 May 1993 to 31 October 2023 for the entire database of 9944 coral reef locations. Subsequently, we quantitatively predicted the bleaching extent by passing the above computed DHW values to the surface and subsurface impact functions.

To evaluate and compare the skills in quantitative predictions of the surface and subsurface model, we performed 10-fold cross validation using the mean absolute error (MAE) as loss function. At each iteration, the testing set was further split into 3 subgroups, grouping corals between 0–10 m, 10–20 m and 20–60 m. The MAE was computed for each of the 3 subgroups, as well as for the entire testing fold. As a second validation and comparison technique, we trained the subsurface calibrated model only with corals located between 0–10 m, 10–20 m and 20–60 m, respectively, and tested it with 10-fold

cross validation. Subsequently, we repeatedly trained the surface model without a specific group of corals, e.g. 0–10 m, and tested it on the omitted group e.g. 0–10 m, comparing the results with the above computed MAE for the subsurface calibrated impact function. The same procedure has been performed with two other subdivision intervals: 3 and 5 m (figure 8). Because the MAE did not vary among subdivision intervals, hereafter we will present only results from the subdivision 0–10 m, 10–20 m, 20–60 m.

3. Results

Statistical analysis of DHW, shown in figures 5(a)–(c), indicates that coral reefs at depths experienced higher DHW values compared to the surface. On average, reefs at 0–10 m, 10–20 m and 20–60 m had higher DHW values by $0.07^\circ\text{C weeks} \pm 1.05^\circ\text{C weeks}$, $0.40^\circ\text{C weeks} \pm 1.87^\circ\text{C weeks}$, and $1.68^\circ\text{C weeks} \pm 5.10^\circ\text{C weeks}$, respectively. In the uppermost 10 m of the water column, the difference in DHW varies, with instances where surface DHW values surpass those at the bottom, contrasting with occasions where bottom DHW values exceed those of the surface. As depth increases from 10 to 20 m and further to 20–60 m, a progressive increase in DHW difference is observed, consistently dropping below zero in reference to the y -axis. This trend indicates a systematic intensification of thermal stress occurring at the seabed level. Additionally, DHW values computed at the time of the bleaching measurements reveal an average difference between surface and bottom DHW for corals within the 0–10 m, 10–20 m, and 20–60 m depth ranges, amounting to $0.19^\circ\text{C weeks} \pm 0.66^\circ\text{C weeks}$, $0.43^\circ\text{C weeks} \pm 1.52^\circ\text{C weeks}$, and

$0.42^{\circ}\text{C weeks} \pm 2.79^{\circ}\text{C weeks}$, respectively. Keeping in mind the scarcity of data points below 20 m, this indicates systematic higher intensities than at the surface across all depth groups for records used in the calibration and testing of our models.

Examination of the model outputs (figures 5(d)–(f)) reveals that the variations in DHWs between different depths translate into discernible differences in bleaching estimates. Coral reefs situated within depth intervals of 0–10 m, 10–20 m, and 20–60 m exhibit divergent bleaching estimates: with subsurface model predicting $1.11\% \pm 4.72\%$, $2.29\% \pm 8.14\%$, and $6.29\% \pm 15.58\%$ higher bleaching compared to the surface model. The analysis of bleaching outputs mirrors the trends observed in the statistical analysis of DHW along the depth gradient. The subsurface modeled bleaching extents consistently favors greater bleaching intensities at greater depths compared to the surface, corroborating the intensified thermal stress observed at greater depths.

An analysis displayed in figure 6 grouping coral reefs in 12 distinct ocean provinces (classified by Donner (2009)), reveals a discernible pattern: while surface and depth models generally align in predicting bleaching extent for regions with shallower average depths, a significant departure from this trend emerges in the Eastern Pacific. This region, featuring a higher proportion of deeper reefs in our dataset, with an average depth of 11 m, exhibits marked disparities between the two models. Reflecting higher DHW values, the bottom model consistently predicts higher bleaching extents compared to the surface model.

Statistical analysis of the 10-fold cross-validation results reveals comparable MAE scores between the surface and depth models across three distinct coral depth groups: 0–10 m, 10–20 m, and 20–60 m. Within the 0–10 m depth range, the subsurface model

recorded 15.01% MAE with the first cross validation method (CV1), in which impact functions were calibrated on all data, and 15.72% MAE with the second cross validation method (CV2), in which impact functions were calibrated by depth interval. Analogously, the surface model scored 14.79% MAE (CV1) and 15.01% MAE (CV2). Similarly, for depths between 10 m and 20 m, the subsurface model yield a MAE of 16.67% (CV1) and 16.03% (CV2), compared to 16.50% (CV1) and 16.52% (CV2) for the surface model. Even for deeper reefs (20–60 m), both models maintain comparably MAE scores, with the subsurface model registering 23.88% (CV1) and 25.25% (CV2), and the surface model 23.79% (CV1) and 24.50% (CV2). In summary, the performance of both the surface and subsurface models on the provided dataset shows no significant difference.

In terms of ETS, the subsurface model scored a cumulative ETS and average ETS across the whole range of categorical thresholds of 21.194 and 0.214 respectively, with a maximal ETS of 0.275 at $\gamma = 10\%$ and an ETS of 0.253 at $\gamma = 30\%$, compared to 0.218 ETS of the only other coral bleaching model from the literature using ETS (DeCarlo 2020) ($\gamma = 30\%$).

4. Discussion

Regarding the optimal length of the AW for defining the DHW, we partially confirm the results of DeCarlo (2020), suggesting 9 weeks, and Lachs *et al* (2021) suggesting 4–8 weeks. When predicting coral bleaching at a specific intensity γ , both 18 weeks or 8 weeks window yield similar performance. The choice of temperature product and coral bleaching dataset might favor one AW over the other. However, for predictions across all bleaching intensities, the 18 week accumulation window is optimal.

In terms of bleaching thresholds, our study supports Lachs *et al* (2021)’s finding that threshold lower than MMM lead to better performing models. While our study indicates that 0 °C performs considerably better than the traditional +1 °C, we found that –1 °C is the best performing threshold.

Our analysis does not suggest significant differences in predictive accuracy between the surface and subsurface model. The congruity observed in MAE scores can be attributed to the statistical characteristics of DHW within our test and calibration dataset. Computing the DHW specifically at the time of coral

Table 3. Repartition of coral reefs through the ocean mixed layer.

	Below MLD (%)	Inside the ML (%)
0–10 m	3.0	97
10–20 m	26.9	73.1
20–60 m	52.1	47.9

bleaching measurements (4594 values), indicates that these values do not exhibit consistent trends along the depth profile with those observed in the entirety of DHW computations (total of 120 million points). Thus, the coral bleaching records from the GCBD, may not effectively reflect differences in performance between the two models.

Furthermore, coral reefs in the GCBD are predominantly situated in the mixed layer (93% of them). As exemplified in table 3, shallow reefs (0–10 m) are almost exclusively in the mixed layer (97%), whereas for reefs located between 10–20 m and 20–60 m the proportion decreases to 73.1% and 47.9% respectively, with the majority (52.1%) of deeper reef (20–60 m) being below the mixed layer depth (MLD). As exemplified by figure 9, coral reefs located below the MLD exhibit higher variability in respect to the surface compared to reefs within the mixed layer. Specifically, extreme differences in DHW between surface and subsurface almost exclusively occurs for coral reefs located below the MLD. Despite these results consolidate our findings, with only 7% of coral reef located below the MLD, a cautionary principle must be applied in the generalization of our findings for reefs below the MLD.

The validity of our results rest upon the assumptions which underpins our modeling framework, that is: (i) the thermal stress which induce coral bleaching is defined upon the local temperature conditions rather than by an absolute threshold, (ii) GLORYS12 reanalysis subsurface temperature is a more accurate estimate of the real temperature experienced at subsurface level by coral reefs compared to GLORYS12 surface temperature (–0.49 m depth) and lastly, (iii) higher thermal stresses, measured with the DHW, leads to higher bleaching extent.

Regarding the first assumption (i), the thermal tolerance of mesophotic corals is lower compared to their surface counterpart (Howells *et al* 2012, Smith *et al* 2016, Skutnik *et al* 2020, Tavakoli-Kolour *et al* 2023). Furthermore, according to Smith *et al* (2016), any temperature anomalies above the local maximum monthly mean may result in thermal stress and coral bleaching, stressing the importance of defining the bleaching threshold based on local temperature. As per assumption (ii), Amaya *et al* (2023a) indicates that GLORYS12 is particularly suited to reproduce nearshore ocean temperature, especially at sea-bed level. For instance, a comparison between GLORYS12 model bottom data with bottom temperature data

from the California west coast bottom trawl survey, indicates a correlation of $r = 0.97$ between the observations and the model reproduction. Following its validation, GLORYS12 has been used in another study by Fredston *et al* (2023), Sun *et al* (2023), Amaya *et al* (2023b) to investigate bottom MHWs at continental shelves. This further reinforces the dataset's reliability for studying sea-bed MHWs in coastal regions.

Regarding (iii), both surface and subsurface calibrated impact functions indicates that the relationship between DHW and coral bleaching is positively monotonic. This result is confirmed by the literature: traditional coral bleaching models attribute DHW values below 4 °C weeks to 'absence of bleaching', DHW between 4 °C weeks and 8 °C weeks to 'bleaching', and DHW's above 8 °C weeks to widespread coral bleaching and in some cases mortality Kayanne (2017).

By calibrating impact functions regionally, we found no significant improvement in modeling accuracy, possibly due to the unbalanced nature of the dataset, having 92% of bleaching records located in the Caribbean. By calibrating different impact functions per depth interval, we observed similar performance, anew possibly because of proportionally more records for shallower reefs. Nevertheless, regionally or depth calibrated impact functions differs in calibration coefficients. Consequently, we speculate that a more geographically and vertically balanced dataset of coral bleaching records, might allow the calibration of regional and depth specific impact functions; further increasing modeling accuracy, as found by DeCarlo (2020).

Furthermore, the scarcity of coral reefs locations below 30 m do not allow the generalization of our findings to other coral reef locations in the same depth range. Because of a decrease in the number of reef locations with depth (8038 between 0–10 m, 1792 between 10–20 m, 114 between 20–60 m), the uncertainty related to our findings increases along the depth gradient. On the other hand, the limited distribution of coral reefs below 30 m is compensated by the high temporal resolution of data collected over a 30 year period, which enables us to robustly confirm the trends observed within the first 30 m of depth; a depth range for which both the spatial and temporal cover are elevated.

While our model predicts the extent of coral bleaching, it is worth noting that coral bleaching may not result in mortality (McClanahan 2004). The response to coral bleaching depends on a number of factors, among which coral taxa and morphology plays a crucial role (McClanahan 2004). Consequently, further refinement of the here proposed model, accounting for recovery rates and species specific characteristics, is needed to infer the mortality caused by a certain bleaching extent.

5. Conclusion

Our study indicates that MHWs are placing upper mesophotic coral reefs under higher thermal stresses compared to their surface counterpart. This undermines the hypothesis that deeper coral reefs might be a refugia from climate change. Furthermore, our analysis indicates a systematic and increasing underestimation of coral bleaching by surface models along the depth gradient 0–60 m, indicating that deeper reefs are in fact not only more threatened than shallower ones, but also that the current state of coral reefs worldwide is more critical than previously thought. With this research, we highlight the importance of increasing the number of coral bleaching records at deeper reefs, allowing to discern whether higher thermal stress at greater depth arises from a selection bias or whether this trend is representative for the entirety of coral reefs. More specifically, localized time series of bleaching records at individual locations might help in isolating the effect of MHWs on coral bleaching, offering the opportunity to increase modeling accuracy by filtering bleaching events caused by different drivers.

Data availability statement

The GLORYS dataset is available from 1 January 1993 to 28 May 2024. The coral database is available from 1980 to 2020. The output data can be obtained in ‘numpy’ format with a size of 813.6 MB. The data that support the findings of this study are openly available at the following URL/DOI: <https://github.com/NicolasColombi/Marine-Heatwaves> (Colombi 2024).

Code availability

Code to reproduce the results of this paper will be made available upon acceptance. For this study, the Python (3.8+) version of CLIMADA (3.2+) can be used Aznar-Siguan *et al* (2023). The source code is openly and freely available under the terms of the GNU General Public License Version 3.

Acknowledgments

This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation program Grant Agreement No 820712 (PROVIDE), No 101073978 (DIRECTED), and No 101081369 (SPARCCLE). This research was also supported by TipESM. TipESM is funded by the European Union (GA 101137673).

Author contributions statement

N C, C M K, and F B conceived and designed the study. N C analyzed the results and wrote the manuscript. N C, C M K, F B, and T F contributed to the interpretation of the results and general framing of the study. D N B provided comments on the manuscripts. All authors reviewed and edited the manuscript.

Conflict of interest

The authors declare no competing interests.

Appendix

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